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Satisfaction with Friendly Relationships in the Italian Regions During the Period 2005-2022

It decreased on average by 11.84%

Istat calculates the value of satisfaction with friendly relationships in the Italian regions. Percentage of people aged 14 and over who are very satisfied with relationships with friends out of the total number of people aged 14 and over. The data refers to the period between 2005 and 2022 for the 20 Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of satisfaction with friendly relationships in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for the value of satisfaction with friendly relationships in 2022 with an amount of 31.2 units, followed by Umbria with an equal value at 26.5 units, and from Veneto with an amount of 25.1 units. In the middle of the table are Lombardy with an amount of 23.4 units, followed by Tuscany with a value of 22.5 units, followed by Sardinia with an amount of 20.8 units. Basilicata closes the ranking with an amount of 17.5 units, followed by Campania with an amount of 16.2 units and Puglia with an amount of 15.9 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in satisfaction with friendship relationships between 2005 and 2022. Calabria is in first place for the value of satisfaction with friendship relationships with a value of 11.05%, rising from 17.20 in 2005 up to 19.10 units in 2022. Valle d'Aosta follows with a variation equal to an amount of 2.89% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 24.20 units in 2005 up to a value of 24.90 in 2022. Finally, Umbria follows with a variation equal to -0.75% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 26.70 units in 2005 up to an amount of 26.50 units in 2022. In the middle of the table was Emilia Romagna with a variation equal to -11.03% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 28.10 units in 2005 up to 25.00 in 2022. Sicily follows with a variation equal to -11.36% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 22.00 units in 2005 up to a value of 19.50 units in 2002. Trentino Alto Adige follows with a variation equal to a variation of -12.85% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 35.80 in 2005 up to an amount of 31.20 units in 2022. Closing the ranking, Basilicata with an amount equal to -23.75% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 22.80 units in 2005 up to a value of 17.50 in 2022. Tuscany follows with a variation equal to an amount of -23.73% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 29.50 units in 2005 equal to a variation of 17.50 units in 2022. Friuli Venezia Giulia closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of -25.23% corresponding to a variation from 32.50 units in 2005 up to an amount of 24.30 units in 2022. On average the value of satisfaction for Friendly relations between 2005 and 2022 in the Italian regions decreased by 11.84%.

Satisfaction with friendly relationships between 2005 and 2022 in the Italian regions. Satisfaction with friendly relationships decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2005 and 2022. In particular, satisfaction with friendly relationships between 2005 and 2022 decreased especially in Central Italy with a value of -19,84%, North-West with -13.67%, Islands with -12.72%, North with -11.83%, Southern Italy with -11.39%, South with -10.53%, North East with -8,90%. In particular,

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the value of satisfaction with friendship relationships between 2005 and 2022 in the South is 31.00% lower than in the North, 29.00% lower than in the North-West, -34.00% lower than in the North - East, -17.00% lower than Central Italy, 5.00% lower than Southern Italy and 15.00% lower than the Islands. It therefore follows that from the point of view of the historical series there is a reduction in satisfaction with friendly relationships in all Italian macro-regions between 2005 and 2022. However, even in the generalized reduction in the value of satisfaction with friendly relationships of verifies an inequality between regions of the Central and Northern Italy, with higher levels of the observed variable, and regions of the South, with reduced values of the variable.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are detected:

- Cluster 1: Sicily, Puglia, Molise, Calabria, Basilicata, Campania, Lazio, Abruzzo, Sardinia, Marche;
- Cluster 2: Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lombardy, Umbria, Tuscany, Veneto, Trentino Alto Adige, Piedmont, Liguria, Valle d'Aosta.

Considering the value of the average of the clusters the following ordering results: $C2 > C1$. It therefore follows that most of the Central-Northern regions have a much higher value of satisfaction with friendly relationships than the corresponding value of the southern regions. Lazio and Marche are the only two regions in Central Italy to participate in Cluster 1, i.e. the Cluster which has a much lower satisfaction value for friendly relationships than in the northern regions.

Conclusions. The value of satisfaction with friendly relationships decreased in the Italian macro-regions between 2005 and 2022. The only two regions in which the value of friendly relationships grew between 2005 and 2022 are Calabria and Valle d'Aosta. If we take the average value of friendship satisfaction between 2005 and 2022 we can notice a significant growth between 2005 and 2012, going from an amount of 24.95 units up to 26.75 units. From 2012 onwards, the value of satisfaction with friendly relationships decreased until reaching a minimum in 2021 with an amount of 19.08 units and then growing to 21.99 in 2022. The reduction in satisfaction with friendly relationships in the regions Italians between 2005 and 2022 is a fact that highlights a change in the structure of Italians' non-family social relationships. The data contrasts with the classic vision of Italians as culturally oriented towards socialization and highlights a change in the character of the population, which could have a very significant impact in terms of reducing the value of human, social and civil capital.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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Appendix

